

Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis: A Review of Hematinic Deficiency Factor

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Abstract:

Background: Recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS) is a common disease of the oral mucosa, with a prevalence of 5-25% in some population in the world. The etiology of RAS is uncertain, but there are several predisposing factors including nutritional factors due to hematinic deficiency, substances that help in the process of erythropoiesis such as vitamin B12, folic acid, and iron. **Aims:** This literature study aims to present the role of hematinic deficiency in the pathogenesis RAS. **Method of review:** This article was created by

searching the PubMed and Scopus databases. **Results:** five studies with the majority using a cross-sectional method and using a sample of 186 to 705 subjects indicate that hematinic deficiency is one of the factors associated with RAS. Three studies state that the RAS group with hematinic deficiency is also associated with anemia, such as microcytic anemia, normocytic anemia, macrocytic anemia, pernicious anemia, and iron deficiency anemia. All studies state that iron deficiency is more common than vitamin B12 and folic acid deficiencies in patients with RAS. Hematinic deficiency causes a decrease capacity of blood to transport oxygen to the oral mucosa, resulting in epithelial atrophy, and this condition is highly susceptible to developing RAS. **Conclusion:** Hematinic deficiency plays a role in the pathogenesis of RAS.

Keywords: Hematinic deficiency, pathogenesis, recurrent aphthous stomatitis.

Introduction

Recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS) is a disease of the oral mucosa which is often found in the form of recurrent ulcerations without other signs of disease (Woo, Setterfield, & Greenberg, 2021). RAS is the most common disease found in the oral cavity, with rates of 5-25% of the world population (Belenguer-Guallar, Jiménez-Soriano, & Claramunt-Lozano, 2014; Compilato, et al., 2010). The clinical appearance of this lesion gives a single or multiple appearance, is round, and is covered by a yellowish or gray-white pseudomembrane and is surrounded by an erythematous halo (Patil, et al., 2014; Apriasari, & Tuti, 2010). Based on its clinical appearance, RAS is classified into major,

minor, and herpetiform RAS (Woo, Setterfield, & Greenberg, 2021).

Recurrent aphthous stomatitis usually causes patients to feel discomfort and pain in the oral mucosa when eating, drinking, and also talking (Yilmaz, et al., 2017). The etiological factors of RAS are not known with certainty, but RAS is caused by multifactors, including genetic, environmental, nutritional factors, smoking, immune abnormalities, stress, trauma, and drugs (Patil, et al., 2014; Ernawati, Soebadi, & Radithia, 2010; Preeti, et al., 2011).

Intake of poor nutrition can affect the health of the body, including affecting the health of the oral cavity (IFPRI IFP, 2016; Gondivkar, et al., 2019). The causes such as poor nutritional

intake, such as consuming lots of fast food that contains lots of sugar, salt, fat and cholesterol. also due to lack of consumption of vitamins and minerals. Data from the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) in 2016, as many as 2 billion of the world's population are deficient in vitamins and minerals (micronutrients) (IFPRI IFP, 2016). Micronutrients that affect the factors that trigger RAS are vitamin B12, iron, and folic acid (Compilato, et al., 2010; McNamee, et al., 2013).

Deficiency of substances that improve blood quality in the process of erythropoiesis such as vitamin B12, folic acid, or iron, which is also called hematinic deficiency, can be identified by changes in the values of several parameters of a complete blood count (McNamee, et al., 2013; Moll, & Davis, 2017). In several studies in Europe, hematinic deficiency has been estimated prevalence with a range of 5% to 46% (McNamee, et al., 2013).

A study conducted by Bao, with a sample of 517 patients diagnosed with RAS, found that 236 (45.6%) of them were related to hematinic deficiency (Bao, et al., 2018). In the study conducted by Lopez, the results showed that 14.4% of RAS patients were associated with a hematinic deficiency (Lopez-Jornet, Camacho-Alonso, & Martos, 2014). Our study found that hematinic level was a significant difference between the RAS and healthy groups for vitamin B-12 levels ($p=0.001$) (Nur'aeny, et al., 2021).

Literature Review

Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis

Recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS) is a disease characterized by recurrent ulcer on the oral mucosa without other signs of disease (Woo, Setterfield, & Greenberg, 2021). Classification of RAS is divided into minor, major, and herpetiform type of RAS.

This major RAS was previously separated, called peradenitis mucosa necrotica recurrens or Sutton's disease (Regezi, Sciubba, & Jordan, 2016). Major RAS is considered the most severe RAS, with a diameter of more than 1 cm and

usually leaves a scar after healing. significant pain and discomfort, and systemic health may be compromised by feeding difficulties and psychological stress (Regezi, Sciubba, & Jordan, 2016).

Minor RAS is the most common finding in patients with RAS. This type usually appears as a single, oval lesion, less than 1 cm in diameter, covered by a yellowish pseudomembrane and surrounded by an erythematous halo (Woo, Setterfield, & Greenberg, 2021; Regezi, Sciubba, & Jordan, 2016).

Herpetiform RAS shows the appearance of small ulcers measuring less than 1 cm, many and recurrent. Unlike viral infections, aphthous herpetiform ulcers are not preceded by vesicles and do not show virus-infected cells. Although the most common predilection is for the movable mucosa, some also occurs for the gingiva and palate.

The etiology of RAS is still unclear. But several factors are known to have a strong relationship with the presence of RAS. Some of them are genetic factors, immune abnormalities, hematological deficiencies, and also local factors (Woo, Setterfield, & Greenberg, 2021). Predisposing factors for RAS are hematinic deficiency, smoking, stress, drugs, and hormonal changes (Chavan, et al., 2012).

Hematinic Deficiency

Iron Deficiency

In humans, iron is an important functional component of many proteins that participate in metabolic functions such as oxygen transport, production of oxidative energy, mitochondrial respiration, and inactivation of harmful oxygen radicals (Moll, & Davis, 2017). Most of the iron in the body is found in heme, which functions as a transport oxygen and protein storage, including hemoglobin and myoglobin (Greer, et al., 2013). In developing countries, the level of iron the body needs each day is 10-15 mg/day of which only 5-10% is absorbed (Moll, & Davis, 2017).

Iron deficiency is the most common deficiency found in nutritional deficiencies, which is usually found in women and children (Kaushansky, et al., 2016). Causes of iron deficiency include chronic blood loss, inadequate iron intake, menstruation, pregnancy, and absorption disorders (Moll, & Davis, 2017; Greer, et al., 2013; Kaushansky, et al., 2016).

Diagnosis of iron deficiency can be made by routine hematological tests for screening as well as tests of serum iron, total iron binding capacity (TIBC), serum ferritin with normal levels of 12–300 ng/ml, and transferrin saturation (Moll, & Davis, 2017). Treatment of iron deficiency is oral iron or parenteral iron therapy (Greer, et al., 2013; Kaushansky, et al., 2016).

Deficiency of Vitamin B12 and Folic Acid

Folic acid is essential for proper brain function and plays an important role in mental and emotional health. Folic acid also helps in the production of DNA and RNA, the body's genetic material, especially when cells and tissues are growing rapidly, such as during infancy, adolescence, and pregnancy. Folic acid works together with vitamin B12 in making red blood cells and helps iron function properly in the body (Moll, & Davis, 2017; Mahmood, 2014).

Vitamin B12 is naturally found in foods including meat (especially liver and shellfish), eggs, and dairy products, while folic acid is found in green vegetables, legumes, whole grains, and liver (Mahmood, 2014; Whitney, & Rofles, 2011).^{20,21} Required intake levels of vitamin B12 is 5-30 ug/day, while folic acid 50 ug/day (Moll, & Davis, 2017).

The causes of vitamin B12 deficiency are lack of consumption of vitamin B12 (usually in individuals who are vegetarians), absorption disorders such as pernicious anemia, ileal resection, and celiac disease. In folic acid

deficiency is usually caused by a lack of consumption which usually occurs in alcoholism, malabsorption, and use of antifolate drugs (Moll, & Davis, 2017).

Diagnostics that can be done are hematological examination and serum vitamin B12 with normal levels of 200–900 pg/ml to detect vitamin B12 deficiency and serum folate with normal levels of 2.7–17 ng/ml, red cell folate, plasma homocysteine to detect folic acid deficiency. Management of vitamin B12 deficiency is giving hydroxocobalamin 1 mg 2-3 times per week for 2 weeks. Management of folic acid deficiency by administering folic acid supplements 5 mg/day for 3-4 months, pregnant women are also given folic acid prophylaxis 400 mg/day (Moll, & Davis, 2017).

Methodology

This research was conducted through a literature review. This study uses two databases to search for data sources, namely PubMed and Scopus. Data search criteria used the keywords "recurrent aphthous stomatitis", "pathogenesis", and "hematinic deficiency".

Articles selected from the database have several criteria that must be met, such as titles and abstracts that must be in accordance with the research objectives, use English, and come from original research or case reports.

Results

The initial search resulted in a total of 9,089 articles, of which 8,996 articles came from the PubMed database, and 93 articles from Scopus. After being evaluated using inclusion and exclusion criteria, 5 appropriate articles were obtained (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the Reviewed Studies

No	Author, Title	Aims	Study type	Number of Subjects	Laboratory Examination	Result
1	The-Xuan Bao, et al. Hematinic deficiencies in patients with recurrent aphthous stomatitis: variations by gender and age	Evaluate the association of hematinic deficiency and RAS.	Cross Sectional	517 RAS patients and 187 controls.	Serum ferritin, folic acid, and vitamin B12.	There was a high frequency (45.6%) of hematinic deficiency in RAS patients. Serum ferritin deficiency is the most common, and is more common in young women and adults under 60 years. Meanwhile, folate and B12 deficiencies are found more frequently in men aged 21-40 years
2	Yang-Che Wndkk. Hematinic deficiencies and antenna statuses in normal aphthous stomatitis patients with or without atrophic glossitis.	Evaluating RAS with atrophic glossitis has hematinic a hemi a/deficiency	Cross Sectional	160AG+/RAS patients, 195 AG-/RAS patients, and 355 healthy control.	MCV, Hb, Iron, B12, Folate serum	Atrophic glossitis +/- has a relationship with the presence of hematinic decrease. However, the frequency of decreased Hb and iron in AG+ patients was more. Of the 69 AG+ anemia, 30 were normocytic anemia, and 23 were def anemia. Iron Of the 38 AG anemic, 26 were normocytic and 5 def. iron.
3	Hung-Pin Lin, et al. Anemia and hematinic deficiencies in anti-gastric parietal cell antibody positive or all autoantibodies negative recurrent aphthous stomatitis patients.	To assess serum GPCA and Abs-status as factors causing anemia/hematinic deficiency in patients with GPCA +/-	Cross Sectional	31GPCA+/RAS patients, 240 Abs-/RAS patients, and 342 healthy control subjects.	MCV, Hb, serum B12, folate and ferritin	The results showed that G PCA+ and RAS patients had a higher frequency of decreased Hb and iron, vitamin B12 than Abs-. This shows that GPCA has an important role in causing vitamin B12 deficiency, high MCV, and homocysteine in GPCA+ RAS patients.
4	Yu-Hsueh Wu, et al. Anemia and hematinic deficiencies in anti-gastric parietal cell antibody-positive and -negative recurrent aphthous stomatitis patients with antithyroid antibody positivity	To assess the association of GPCA, TGA, and IMA in causing anemia and hematinic deficiency in RAS patients	Cross Sectional	84 TGA TMA +, 240abs-, 342 healthy control	CBC, Hb, serum	Serum G PCA and RAS were found to be contributing factors to anemia and hematinic deficiency.
5	Pia Lopez-Jomet, et al. Hematological study of patients with aphthous stomatitis.	Evaluate the association of deficiency of iron, vitamin B12, and folic acid.	Cross Sectional	92 subjects with RAS, 94 controls	Blood counts and sera	Routine hematological screening and tests of serum iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12 should be assessed in all patients with RAS. The overall frequency of hematinic deficiency was 14.4% in the RAS group compared to 6.39% in the control group. Age and family history are found in the presence of RAS.

The samples used in the study conducted by the authors of the articles varied from 186 to 705 patients. All articles use the cross-sectional method in conducting research, the results of

which are written in English. All studies used tests of serum vitamin B12, folic acid, iron to determine hematinic deficiency. Four studies conducted routine blood tests to screen for

hematinic deficiency, and 2 studies conducted serum GPCA tests to assess their involvement in patients with anemia and hematinic deficiency.

Discussion

This literature review focuses on discussing the role of hematinic deficiency in the pathogenesis of RAS. In the study conducted by Lopez, 14.14% of RAS patients had hematinic deficiency (Lopez-Jornet, Camacho-Alonso, & Martos, 2014).

Xuan Bao conducted a study on hematinic deficiency in RAS patients, based on gender and age variations. The sample used was 517 patients diagnosed with minor RAS in the oral disease department of Shanxi Provincial Hospital, China. The results obtained are that iron deficiency generally affects female RAS patients with an age range of 21-40 years (34%), and vitamin B12 deficiency is the majority in male RAS patients aged ≥ 61 years (46.7%). and folic acid deficiency mostly suffered by men aged ≤ 20 years (19.4%) (Bao, et al., 2018).

Iron deficiency can cause microcytic anemia, while deficiency of vitamin B12 and folic acid can cause macrocytic anemia. RAS patients with anemia and lower Hb levels can reduce the capacity of blood to carry oxygen to the oral mucosa, which eventually causes atrophy of the oral mucosa. In addition, iron is essential for the normal function of oral epithelial cells and vitamin B12 and folic acid play important roles in DNA synthesis and cell division. Oral epithelial atrophy in patients with hematinic deficiency may explain why some patients with hematinic deficiency tend to have RAS (Lin, et al., 2017; Vanjani, Phulari, & Rathore, 2019).

In a study conducted by Yu-Hsueh Wu, described the relationship of anti-gastric parietal cell (GPCA) serum in relation to hematinic deficiency and anemia in RAS patients. GPCA can cause damage to gastric parietal cells, then cause failure of intrinsic factor production. Complete or partial loss of intrinsic factor can lead to vitamin B12 deficiency which eventually results in macrocytosis and pernicious anemia status. Deficiency of vitamin B12 and folic acid

can lead to high serum homocysteine levels in patients with oral mucosal disease. However, supplementation of some B vitamins, especially vitamin B12 and folic acid, can reduce serum homocysteine levels in patients with atrophic glossitis or burning mouth syndrome. Deficiency of vitamin B12 can lead to significantly reduced Hb production. In addition, vitamin B12 deficiency can inhibit purine and thymidylate synthesis, impair DNA synthesis, and cause erythroblast apoptosis, leading to anemia due to ineffective erythropoiesis. Yu-Hsueh Wu also conducted tests related to anti-thyroglobulin (TGA), and anti-thyroid microsomal antibodies (TMA) in RAS patients, and the results showed that TGA/TMA did not have an important role in causing anemia and hematinic deficiency (Wu, et al., 2016).

This study also explains the attachment to RAS which can also be a factor causing anemia and haematinic deficiency in RAS patients. A previous dietary history questionnaire study showed significantly lower daily intake of vitamin B12 and folic acid in patients with minor types of RAS than in control subjects. These findings indicate that the presence of ulceration in the mouth either single or multiple can cause daily intake of vitamin B12 and folate to decrease.

Atrophic glossitis is also found in patients with hematinic deficiency. Atrophic glossitis as well as the presence of severe ulcerative lesions of the oral mucosa can cause a burning sensation and pain when the patient eats salty and spicy foods. This can cause difficulty eating and reduced intake of incoming food, causing anemia and haematinic deficiency (Vanjani, Phulari, & Rathore, 2019).

Conclusion

Hematinic deficiency is one of the factors that play a role in the pathogenesis of recurrent aphthous stomatitis, and vice versa. Therefore, it is hoped that dentists will carry out routine hematological screening of patients with RAS to find out the triggering factors that can lead to RAS.

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